

D8.12

Atmospheric subdomain development strategy

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Deliverable abstract

This report presents a synthesis of the progress of FAIRness for the atmospheric subdomain in the project with links to relevant documents. Furthermore, the report provides a strategy for the future development of the atmospheric subdomain and common recommendations to consolidate the atmospheric subdomain contribution beyond the ENVRI-FAIR project.

DELIVERY SLIP

	Name	Partner Organization	Date
Main Author	Cathrine Lund Myhre	NILU/ACTRIS, Norway	19 June 2023
Contributing Authors	Damien Boulanger Markus Fiebig Anders Tjulin Leo Rivier Lara Ferrighi	CNRS/IAGOS, France NILU/ACTRIS, Norway EISCAT, Sweden LSCE/ICOS ERIC, France MET Norway, SIOS, Norway	
Reviewer(s)	Alex Vermeulen	ICOS ERIC, Sweden	22 June 2023
Approver	Andreas Petzold	FZJ	23 June 2023

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V 0.1	19 June 2023		Cathrine Lund Myhre

DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

A relevant project glossary is included in Appendix A. The latest version of the master list of the glossary is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471374>.

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent, and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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D8.12 – Atmospheric subdomain development strategy

1 Introduction and background

The ENVRI-FAIR project's objective is to implement "FAIRness" for data produced in the European Research Infrastructures (RIs), organized in the Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) community, in order to make them ready for connecting to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). In this context, "FAIR" is an acronym comprising the aspects of "Findable", "Accessible", "Interoperable", and "Reusable" as specified by the [FORCE11 community](#).

ENVRI-FAIR WP8 organises and conducts this implementation work for the community of ENVRI RIs in the atmospheric subdomain, comprised of the RIs [ACTRIS](#), [EISCAT](#), [IAGOS](#), [ICOS](#) (atmosphere), and [SIOS](#) (atmosphere). Box 1 provides more information about the RIs.

The main objective for the atmospheric domain within ENVRI-FAIR has been to advance the FAIRness of the atmospheric subdomain, by implementation of technological solutions on RI level to improve access to data and services.

The atmospheric RIs agreed to a main strategy and goal:

"To increase use of data for all users by learning from each other and take advantage of synergies and common solutions when feasible and beneficial to serve our existing users and attract and serve new users."

This deliverable will synthesise the progress of FAIRness and provide a strategy for future development of the atmospheric subdomain. This report includes common recommendations to consolidate the Atmospheric subdomain contribution beyond ENVRI-FAIR project.

The atmospheric RIs within ENVRI landscape are targeting:

- Climate change, both natural and anthropogenic changes
- Air pollution and air quality,
- Natural hazards impacting the atmosphere as fires, desert storms, extreme precipitation,
- Space weather with impact on surface infrastructures and on satellite communication.

The RIs compile in total at least 130 variables on atmospheric composition or properties, of which about 75 variables are reactive trace gases, distributed over 5 RIs. The RIs are handling data in RRT (< 3 hour), NRT (< 3 days), and quality assured data. The 5 RIs are covering the atmospheric subdomain, including 2 multi-domain RIs with an atmospheric component (ICOS and SIOS). The RIs are:

[ACTRIS](#) – Aerosol Cloud and Trace gases Research Infrastructure

[EISCAT-3D](#) European Incoherent Scatter radar system

[IAGOS](#) – In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System

[ICOS – atm](#): Integrated Carbon Observation System – atmospheric component

[SIOS-atm](#): Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System - atmospheric component

2 Synthesise the progress of FAIRness

The development strategy is depending on the current situation and FAIRness level of the RIs. This section points to the documents and reports with the description of the present state.

A set of deliverables has been produced to describe the present state of FAIRness of the atmospheric subdomain. These are based on a comprehensive FAIRness assessment in 2018-2019 that resulted in a detailed implementation plan on RI level, taking cross-RI aspects into account. [D8.3 Atmospheric subdomain implementation plan](#) is the implementation plan of FAIRness for the atmospheric subdomain with a [revised version from September 2021](#), taking the implementation of the new ENVRI-hub into account. In accordance with these plans, the following deliverables describe the FAIRness on RI level

No	title	DOI
D8.4	The FAIRness of ACTRIS	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7741417
D8.5	The FAIRness of EISCAT_3D	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7780170
D8.6	The FAIRness of IAGOS	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7708586
D8.7	The FAIRness of ICOS	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7945027
D8.8	The FAIRness of SIOS	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7695573

Furthermore, a full FAIRness assessment of the subdomain was performed March – April 2023 and compared to the development since start. The comparison is reported in D8.13 Atmospheric subdomain FAIRness assessment report with this DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8026841>

An example showing the FAIR development across the RIs is shown in Figure 1. The figure visualises the total count of FAIR enabling resources (FER) shared between each pair of RIs in the subdomain, a measure of FAIR convergence, and the development of these numbers over the period 2019-2022.

Figure 1 The total count of shared FERs for any pair of RIs has in common accumulated for all FAIR sub-principles

The detailed analyses, presented in [D8.13 Atmospheric subdomain FAIRness assessment report](#), shows that the main improvement is within the “Findable”, Interoperable and Re-Usable concepts, as the “Accessible” resources where more mature.

One relevant topic for motivation and outlining the next steps is to present an overview of what we can do now, which we could not before advancing of the FAIRness, included in section 2.1.1

2.1 What can we do now which we could not before advancing of the FAIRness?

Each RI has provided input on what can be done now, that was not possible before the recent implementation of FAIRness. This is also demonstrated in [Deliverable D8.9 - Demonstrator of implemented service](#), which provides a status of showcases from May 2023.

Here we highlight the joint achievements across the subdomain that are opening new opportunities and synergies and that will important for later work and collaboration within the subdomain. This information is also available in more detail in [D8.13 - Atmospheric subdomain FAIRness assessment report](#) but for completeness, it is also included here.

2.1.1 Joint achievements of FAIRness for the atmospheric subdomain

There has been strong progress and evolution of FAIRness within the atmospheric subdomain, and convergence to common solutions over the project period. This section highlights the joint achievements across the subdomain opening new opportunities and synergies.

Figure 2: Joint achievements across the atmospheric subdomain

The next illustration highlights the atmospheric subdomain achievements towards the ENVRI-FAIR goals.

Figure 3: Atmospheric subdomain achievements towards the ENVRI-FAIR goals

3 Strategy for future development of the atmospheric subdomain

The work and development in ENVRI-FAIR has been highly valuable and well documented in the FAIRness reports referred to in section 2. The in-depth documents referred to in section 2 form the starting point for further technical development. In addition, each RI has provided a summary of their specific aims and priorities for achievements in the next 5 years to seek potential for common goals for development and work, presented in the next sections.

3.1 What would we like to do / achieve within the next 5 years?

Each RI has provided their core priorities for the next years as a basis for identification core topics for joint and future collaboration.

3.1.1 ACTRIS priorities for future development

This is the list of priorities for the next years have been provided by ACTRIS Data Centre:

- Improving and enhancing the link between ACTRIS and EOSC, GEO, Copernicus.
 - E.g., continue to integrate ACTRIS services in EOSC marketplace
- Continue to develop cross RI services across the (sub)domain
- Implement a new data portal with human graphical interface that makes use of all FAIRness achievements so far
 - vocabulary, easier machine data access, data streaming
 - empowering search synergistic capability on ACTRIS data portal
- work on machine actionability, provide user friendly API and develop on-demand processing services (through OGC WPS for instance)
=> dashboards or VREs (to cover either generic or specific needs), and maybe allow some users to build their own
- Implement service for identification of data collections.
- Fully implement documentation of data provenance and make the information accessible and usable for the data user.
- CoreTrustSeal certification of the data centre, including functional test of all FAIRness features.
- Make metadata available in RDF compatible format.
- Implement EOSC-compatible single-sign-on mechanism for services requiring authentication.
- Implement quantification of data use feature based on OpenAire API.
- Cross-RI searching capability on RI portals (for example possibility on ACTRIS portal to query ICOS data for variables of interest in the same period /close by stations...)
- improve the colocation tool and support more satellite data, for atmospheric science but also extended to solid earth, marine and surface observation
- include multi-domain VRE based on these services.
- Further improvements on data provenance and traceability by providing for all new datasets (experiments) as a mandatory fields: a control experiment, the auxiliary mechanism (see DMP), the ORCID of the data provider, a flagging system providing information on the quality level of the data, assignment of PID to instruments

In addition to section 2.1 in [D8.13 - Atmospheric subdomain FAIRness assessment](#) provides more details on the remaining implementation tasks.

Here, the topics for ACTRIS are mainly related to implementation of provenance documentation, common minimum profile of provenance items documented.

3.1.2 EISCAT priorities for future development

This is the list of priorities for the next years provided by EISCAT.

- To have the new EISCAT_3D ready and producing data of high quality, and accordingly have a FAIR data archive for the EISCAT_3D data ready.
- To enable searches for patterns of data (for instance looking for signatures of specific ionospheric conditions).
- To ensure completeness of the datasets, and to have the metadata harvestable in selectable formats.
- To have PIDs available where it is relevant (for citable datasets, notebooks, workflows, etc).
- To ensure that the (extended) EISCAT community will be familiar with all of the above.

In addition to section 2.1 in [D8.13 - Atmospheric subdomain FAIRness assessment](#) provides more details on the remaining implementation tasks.

Here, the topics for EISCAT are mainly related to the delays in the construction of the EISCAT_3D system which have led to delays in the FAIRness implementation connected to the new system.

3.1.3 IAGOS priorities for future development

This is the list of priorities for the next years provided by IAGOS:

- Implement more interoperable services (e.g. VRE)
- Improving and enhancing the link between IAGOS and EOSC, Copernicus.
 - e.g., Integrate all IAGOS resources (services and datasets) in EOSC marketplace.g. Further develop/improve the transmission of IAGOS data in near(real)-real time for Copernicus
- Further improvements of the cross-RI searching capability on RI portals (as recently developed for ACTRIS, ICOS-Atm and IAGOS in the frame of the ATMO-ACCESS project...)
- Implement quantification of data use feature based on OpenAire API.

In addition to section 2.1 in [D8.13 - Atmospheric subdomain FAIRness assessment](#) provides more details on the remaining implementation tasks.

3.1.4 ICOS-atm priorities for future development

This is the list of priorities for the next years provided by ICOS.

- Implement and map ontologies that describe the different data systems from the RIs,
- implement metadata profiles using the iso19156 (OMS) standard and schema.org,
- describing the measurements using I-Adopt
- integrate with WMO WMDR2 development and WIS2 data flows
- Implement Keycloak and connect the ICOS Single Sign On system to ENVRI and EOSC AAI
- Implement iAdopt ontology to better describe the observed properties in community vocabularies and publish metadata through mapping to WMDR2 and data through WIS2
- Add an OAI-PMH service that lists our Datacite DOI and ISO19115 metadata records for syncing our data repository to GEOSS, B2FIND and OpenAire

In addition to section 2.1 in [D8.13 - Atmospheric subdomain FAIRness assessment](#) provides more details on the remaining implementation tasks.

3.1.5 SIOS priorities for future development

This is the list of priorities for next years provided by SIOS.

- Change the back end and indexing of the M2M endpoint to allow for different metadata output to be exposed.
- Interact with WMO for exposing data from aggregators in WIS
- Update the vocabulary server to Docker and extend it to host mapping capabilities between CF standard names and GCMD NASA Earth Science Keyword
Release the landing page generator for METNO
- Automatize the request for DOI at METNO
- Work on integrating data citation counts services on the data portal
- Better use of the vocabulary service to enrich metadata records
- Provide better visualization services for the data portal
- Further enhance standardization of harvested metadata records

In addition to section 2.1 in [D8.13 - Atmospheric subdomain FAIRness assessment](#) provides more details on the remaining implementation tasks.

3.2 Recommendations for next steps and near future

ENVRI-FAIR has been very successful for the atmospheric-subdomain, resulting in improvements in many fields related to FAIRness, and FAIR convergence within the subdomain. Important understanding and strong collaboration have been established across the subdomain on various levels, tasks, and topics, covering:

- Strategic discussions within the data centre coordination, leadership and work,
- with working groups on targeted topics involving people with complementary background and skills and
- technical collaboration at the system development level.

The knowledge about the data, data products, services and organization and coordination of the data centers within the atmospheric subdomain has increased considerably between all RIs and will facilitate further collaboration and joint development.

Here we highlight 6 core statements as intent for future evolvement and collaboration:

Statement 1: Common vision and seek collaboration on proposals

As an overarching strategic goal for future development of the atmospheric subdomain we keep the common statement developed during the first phase of the project:

“To increase use of data for all users by learning from each other and take advantage of synergies and common solutions when feasible and beneficial to serve our existing users and attract and serve new users. “

Statement 2: Shared and open implementation plans.

As an indication of workplan we will continue to use the implementation plan on RI level, and also the [D8.13 - Atmospheric subdomain FAIRness assessment](#) documenting the gaps on RI level.

These documents can serve as relevant input for new and upcoming calls, identify common topics for work and establish collaboration on common shortcomings as e.g. provenance across the RIs where several of the RIs needs more development and implementation.

Statement 3: Continue to work towards convergence of solutions.

Due to the strong development in convergence with respect to many FAIR aspects over the project we do now have seamless integration across the atmospheric subdomain for our users in many aspects. There is a possibility to implement cross RI services thanks to the convergence between RIs on important topics such as vocabularies, identifiers, and licences. Noteworthy, CC BY4.0¹ has become a community

¹ [Creative Commons — Attribution 4.0 International — CC BY 4.0](#)

standard for licensing of data within the atmospheric subdomain. Furthermore, the controlled vocabulary extending beyond the respective RIs has enabled better integration across the subdomains and opened new opportunities for development of new products and work in the near future.

Statement 4: Agree to common single sign on solution

The RIs within the domain should aim for common EOSC compatible single sign on solution and service. This will facilitate the use of the atmospheric subdomain data and services provided to EOSC significantly.

Statement 5: Aim for development of cross RI subdomain products.

The well documented successful collaboration in ENVIR-FAIR and the strong evolvement of FAIR convergence across the subdomain has opened many new opportunities and possibilities of new products. This can lead to many new highly valuable scientific services and achievements. One example is already evolved to new services for users within the project ATMO-ACCESS and the virtual access services developed and offered to all users there: [Virtual Access – ATMO-ACCESS](#). Here e.g. parts of the FAIR demonstrator ([Deliverable D8.9 - Demonstrator of implemented service](#)), is further developed for the users.

Statement 6: Aim for coordinating the representation of the subdomain standardisation groups, e.g., in RDA and EOSC context

There are many ongoing often challenging or complex processes where joint and common representation will be a beneficial for atmospheric subdomain. Over the next period we should elaborate on how we can coordinate this and e.g. our representation in standardization groups, e.g. in RDA and EOSC context to the benefit for the subdomain and RIs.

3.2.1 The atmospheric subdomain contribution to ENVRI-hub and EOSC, next steps

Contribution to the [EOSC Marketplace](#) is high on the agenda and central for the atmospheric subdomain, and it is considered important for all RIs also over the next years. Core and major services developed by the RIs, including cross-RI services, have been described in the ENVRI Catalogue of services envri-hub.envri.eu/cservicesmain, and made available within the ENVRI-hub. Most of these services are also registered in the in the EOSC Marketplace. Most RIs have added their services both places. The status of the cataloguing is detailed in “[Milestone MS51 - Atmospheric subdomain services in service catalogue for exposure to EOSC](#)”. However, this is more a snapshot of the situation in May 2023, and constantly developing as the RIs are adding more services.